

"IT'S PRONOUNCED 'TOTE': LESSONS LEARNED FROM BUILDING AN OPEN BOOK FUTURE WITH THOTH"

Gareth Cole

Loughborough University
United Kingdom
g.j.cole@lboro.ac.uk
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7493-0137>

Paul Stokes

Jisc
United Kingdom
paul.stokes@jisc.ac.uk
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7333-4998>

Ross Higman

Ross Higman
United Kingdom
ross@openbookpublishers.com

Jenny Fry

Loughborough University
United Kingdom
j.fry@lboro.ac.uk
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3110-1683>

Rupert Gatti

Open Book Publishers
United Kingdom
rupert.gatti@openbookpublishers.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0676-9024>

Toby Steiner

Thoth
United Kingdom
toby@thoth.pub
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3158-3136>

Paul Wheatley

Independent
United Kingdom
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3839-3298>

Holly Turpin

Loughborough University
United Kingdom
h.turpin@lboro.ac.uk
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0214-3883>

Abstract – Throughout the COPIM and OBF projects, the Archiving and Preservation work package team has gained valuable insights into the archiving challenges faced by smaller open-access publishers and how to tackle them. Engaging with stakeholders, conducting desk research, and diving into technical investigations have revealed a more complex picture than was initially expected. Armed with this knowledge, the team is now focused on developing an effective, flexible archiving solution that aligns with open-access principles.

This paper presents some of the challenges encountered, how they were overcome, and how the project intends to progress as it enters its final year.

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I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

COPIM is a collaborative community of individuals and organizations dedicated to community-led, values-driven initiatives that support open access authors, publishers, and readers. Originally established through the Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs (COPIM) project (2019–2023)[1], the COPIM community continues to expand and evolve through its ongoing work on the Open Book Futures project (2023–2026)[2] and other related activities.

The Open Book Futures project is funded by Arcadia[3] and the Research England Development (RED) Fund[4]. Building on the pioneering efforts of the COPIM project (2019–2023), this initiative is led by Lancaster University. Open Book Futures aspires

to significantly enhance the ambition, scope, and impact of community-led Open Access book publishing.

The project as a whole has the stated objectives of:

1. Enhancing the impact of the approaches and infrastructures developed within the COPIM project
2. Bridging the infrastructure gap
3. Incubating and financially supporting open access initiatives
4. Enhancing engagement with the wider OA publishing ecosystem
5. Fostering bibliodiversity
6. Support emerging OA books policy guidance

Work Package 7—the work package the authors are closely involved with—deals with the challenges faced in the open publishing world when it comes to Archiving and Digital Preservation.

A. First Steps and Challenges

Early in the project, addressing the archiving/preservation aspect problems faced by small, open access, book publishers, a proposal to create the Thoth Archiving Network was introduced: connecting smaller publishers with institutional repositories to host archive copies of their works. A key consideration was to provide a low cost and easy solution for smaller publishers using existing repositories, but a second motivation was recognising that existing archiving solutions were not designed specifically for open access content and did not make the either the content or the archiving processes open and transparent.

Despite several logistical and technical challenges, potential network participants were broadly supportive and willing to collaborate on solutions. The team proceeded to expand the Network by adding new 'nodes' while refining existing workflows with the Loughborough Figshare repository[5] and Internet Archive[6]. A partnership was established with Cambridge University Library[7], and a test integration with the Zenodo API[8] was completed. Throughout this process, the team continuously monitored and reflected on both existing and emerging challenges to ensure the approach met publishers' needs.

B. Scoping Out a Way Forward

With a proof of concept established by connecting to four repositories, the team met to consider next steps. User stories for stakeholders, including authors, publishers, repository owners, libraries, readers, and funders, were brainstormed to identify objectives an "open" archiving solution could achieve. Using the MoSCoW[9] method, potential deliverables were prioritized.

A smaller team then translated these user requirements into software features. For example, ensuring trust in the accuracy of archived content might involve a verification component. Current and potential 'nodes' of the Archiving Network were assessed for these features, and implementation routes were explored. The technical lead documented these conclusions in a technical specification, which was reviewed and approved by the full team.

1. Targeting Key Features of an Open Archiving Solution

The Thoth Archiving Network, now the Thoth Open Archiving Network (TOAN), focuses on capturing unarchived publications while embedding principles of openness into every aspect of the workflow.

Essential features for an open archiving solution include:

- Openly accessible content
- Openly accessible metadata
- Openly verifiable processes:
 - Publishing checksums for content integrity verification
 - Transparent version control for content and metadata
 - Clear mechanisms for content maintenance
- Reliability and long-term sustainability
 - Multiple geographically-redundant copies

Highly desirable features include:

- Support for archiving associated content
- Clearly-stated content removal policies
- Usage statistics collation
- Independence from private or government entities

The first essential attribute—openly accessible content—might seem self-evident. However, many existing archiving solutions are designed to handle copyrighted items and therefore do not make content openly available until deemed necessary. Much like in discussions the project has had with national libraries, stakeholders who are open to this change often find that established workflows hinder practical implementation. The focus will now shift to archives that make content fully public from the point of deposit while also ensuring reliability and transparency. Investigations have shown that high-capacity generalist repositories are often best equipped to provide these crucial features.

As a first pass—a Minimum Viable product—the team will ensure all TOAN content and metadata is archived in both Internet Archive and Zenodo, while maintaining partnerships with Loughborough University and Cambridge University Library repositories. To connect these archives into a network, additional open-source, verifiable software features are being developed, building on the Thoth metadata system.

II. CONCLUSIONS – THE WORK CONTINUES

This revised plan for TOAN offers small open-access publishers a low-cost, frictionless archiving option and paves the way for new archiving approaches in an open-access landscape. By focusing on a core group of repositories, a transparent, effective archiving system that empowers both publishers and readers can be developed.

In the coming weeks and months, desk research will continue to draft a comprehensive comparative overview of existing archiving solutions and their suitability for open-access works. These reports, along with the TOAN proof of concept, aim to form a blueprint for 'open archiving' and influence broader discussions on archiving and preservation within an open-access framework.

The authors anticipate presenting these findings at a future conference.

REFERENCES

- [1] <https://copim.pubpub.org/copim-project>
- [2] <https://copim.pubpub.org/open-book-futures-project>
- [3] <https://www.arcadiafund.org.uk/>

- [4] <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/research-england-development-fund/>
- [5] https://repository.lboro.ac.uk/Thoth_Archiving_Network
- [6] <https://archive.org/details/thoth-archiving-network>
- [7] <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/thoth-archiving-network-goes-live-at-university-of-cambridge>
- [8] <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth-dissemination/blob/402ba502da63291f21e359a263a12317872d3b9d/zenodouploader.py>
- [9] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MoSCoW_method

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Gareth Cole is the Open Research Lead at Loughborough University. He also leads on the University Archive and copyright. He holds a PhD from the University of Exeter. He co-leads the archiving and preservation work package on the Open Book Futures project.

Paul Stokes has had a career in both the commercial sector and academia. At present he leads on preservation for Jisc. He is a director of the DPC and the OPF. He's passionate about repositories, preservation and all things green and has a bee in his bonnet regarding value, sustainability, carbon costs, and storage.

Ross Higman has been involved in developing the open-source metadata management system Thoth since its early days, with a particular focus on integrating it with third-party platforms to automate book dissemination. Early work experience of data entry for a publishing company inspired him to learn to make computers do it instead.

Jenny Fry is a Professor of Publishing and Information Science at Loughborough University. Her research is focused on digital scholarship.

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Toby Steiner is the Product Manager and Chief Operating Officer of Thoth. Prior to this he was the project manager on the Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs (COPIM) project. He is interested in exploring Open Scholarship practices - currently with a focus on scholar- and community-led OA books and open infrastructure for the Humanities and Social Sciences.

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Holly Turpin is the Research Associate on the archiving and preservation work package of the Open Book Futures project. She is just completing her PhD at Loughborough University in Immersive Digital Storytelling.

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